

Citizen Science in Schools - Experiences of Project Leaders

This report presents findings from focus groups with Australian citizen science project leaders (August 2021) with interest in and/or experiences with engaging young people in citizen science.

The aim of this study was to understand the implementation of citizen science in Australian schools and the underlying advantages, challenges, and perceived outcomes.

Findings are based on:

- Five focus groups conducted with 17 citizen science project leaders from across 6 Australian states and territories
- Representatives from 18 unique citizen science projects

Student advantages from participation in citizen science

Project leaders shared the many advantages they observed for students through participation in their projects. These advantages were classified into the following categories:

Enablers – unique factors of citizen science projects that increase interest in science involvement for students.

Engagers – qualities of participation that increase student engagement in citizen science.

Enactors – factors that empower students beyond their participation in citizen science.

Challenges implementing citizen science in schools

As demonstrated, project leaders described many advantages for the use of citizen science in schools. However, they also shared several challenges experienced while implementing citizen science within school settings.

Citizen science project leaders may not have the necessary **resources and knowledge** to run school projects

Balancing the **science and education aspects** of citizen science can result in compromises in school settings

Student online and physical **safety** is an important consideration; can impact scope of project activities

Time is a scarce resource for teachers

Varied teacher confidence in science; some teachers may require extra assistance to run projects

Citizen science projects **do not always align well with formal curriculum**

Connecting and collaborating with teachers can be difficult when teachers are unfamiliar with citizen science, or project leaders unfamiliar with schools

Next steps

This research will be used to inform the development of our school citizen science projects. We are working to investigate many of the ideas discussed from multiple perspectives, including those of teachers and educational designers. This research has also inspired the initiation of two new projects, mapping citizen science to the Australian curriculum and the development of an evaluative framework for citizen science learning outcomes.

For more information on our research projects see: <https://lbdscience.com/learning-by-doing-research>

We would like to thank all of the citizen science project leaders that participated in this research for sharing their experiences and ideas about school implementation of citizen science in Australia.

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